

Sexy ways: the methodical approaches to study plant sex chromosomes

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Highlight

This review explores adapted or newly developed methods customized for comprehensive analysis of sex chromosomes in dioecious plants. We emphasize methodological approaches for understanding of XY chromosome structure and function.

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Abstract

Sex chromosomes have evolved in many plant species with separate sexes. Current plant research is shifting from examining the structure of sex chromosomes to exploring their functional aspects. New studies are progressively unveiling the specific genetic and epigenetic mechanisms responsible for shaping distinct sexes in plants. While the fundamental methods of molecular biology and genomics are generally employed for the analysis of sex chromosomes, it is often necessary to modify classical procedures not only to simplify and expedite analyses but sometimes to make them possible at all. In this review, we demonstrate how, at the level of structural and functional genetics, cytogenetics, and bioinformatics, it is essential to adapt established procedures for sex chromosome analysis.

Keywords: sex chromosomes, dioecious plants, chromosome dissection, transposable elements, epigenetics, cytogenetics, functional genetics, bioinformatics, tandem repeats

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Introduction

Dioecy represents an extreme strategy of sexual reproduction where sex-specific structures emerge on distinct plants. The existence of different sexes frequently gives rise to what are known as sex chromosomes (typically X and Y or Z and W). The widespread occurrence of recombination suppression within sex chromosomes is a common evolutionary trend, typically accompanied by degeneration and the loss of genes in the non-recombining region of the sex-limited chromosome (Y or W) (Fig. 1). The evolution of the Y (W) or Yh in papaya (VanBuren *et al.*, 2015; Yue *et al.*, 2022) chromosome involves key stages such as the establishment of the sex-determining region, suppression of recombination, accumulation of repeats, gene degeneration, and reduction through deletions. Expansion and shrinkage are frequently concurrent processes that shape the Y chromosome structure, exerting varying impacts on Y chromosome dynamics throughout different stages of sex chromosome evolution (Vyskot and Hobza, 2015).

The nature and complexity of sex chromosomes often demands cutting-edge technologies for comprehensive analyses of their evolution and correct assembly of non-recombining regions (Fig. 1). Consequently, classical methods in genetics that utilize genetic maps for comparative analyses, genome rearrangement analysis, and gene identification, are limited due to the repetitive fraction within the sex chromosomes and suppressed recombination. Even genetic mapping based on deletion mutant lines can be challenging if those deletions are lethal during gametogenesis. The approach to avoid this limiting factor was for a long time in use of radiation hybrid (RH) or HAPPY mapping approaches (for a review see Riera-Lizarazu *et al.*, 2008). However, the application of these methods in plants is still in the experimental phase and quite challenging. Currently, the large progress in methods improving genome assemblies, e.g. optical genome mapping, makes study of long non-recombining regions more feasible. This progress opens avenues for deeper exploration, potentially uncovering novel insights into sex chromosome evolution and facilitating more accurate assembly of non-recombining regions. The integration of 3rd generation sequencing techniques, supported by functional analysis and cytogenetics, will not only enhance our current understanding on sex chromosome origin, and the role of chromosomal rearrangements during sex chromosome formation, but also paves the way for future discoveries regarding the non-recombining region and evolutionary strata.

In this review, we aim to highlight some peculiarities of sex chromosome analysis resulting from the aforementioned aspects. The purpose of the review is not to enumerate successful applications of individual methods across all plant species with sex chromosomes but to demonstrate their suitability and utility through specific examples.

Dissecting sex chromosomes: a swift transition from disorder to understanding

Laser microdissection and chromosome sorting of plant chromosomes represent distinctive technology designed to simplify the analysis of large plant genomes by physical separation of their specific parts (Fig. 2). Flow sorting is a method of choice when a large volume of high-molecular-weight DNA suitable for further detailed analysis is required. The flow sorting is

relatively easy to use and once adopted (e.g. time or strength of fixative), it takes usually from several hours up to several days. In contrast, chromosome microdissection typically ensures higher purity of isolated chromosomes (almost 100%) and it might be usable for a wider range of applications (Hobza and Vyskot, 2007; Soares *et al.*, 2020). Nevertheless, both manual and laser beam-based microdissection methods provide significantly smaller amounts of material compared to flow sorting technology. Moreover, microdissection-based methods rely heavily on the expertise of the personnel involved and the collection of plant material may take several days up to weeks.

In plants, chromosome sorting and microdissection techniques have been extensively applied, particularly in the analysis of sex chromosomes. Indeed, the dissection of the largest chromosome in spinach (*Spinacia oleracea*) and its amplification by DOP-PCR helped to identify male specific marker (T11A) that was isolated from amplified DNA (Onodera *et al.*, 2008). This led to the direct evidence of the Y chromosome. The X/Y chromosomes in spinach were recently assembled using single-chromosome sequencing and the advantage of manual microdissection (Li *et al.*, 2023). Aside of identification of sex-specific markers and sequencing projects, the microdissection of single-chromosomes further helped to develop complex chromosome painting probes as in the case white campion (*Silene latifolia*) (Hobza *et al.*, 2004) and Japanese hop (*Humulus japonicus*) (Yakovin *et al.*, 2014). Alternative applications fulfil diverse objectives, including the targeted development of DNA markers and the construction of DNA libraries (Požárková *et al.*, 2002; Hobza *et al.*, 2006), physical mapping of individual markers and genes (Cegan *et al.*, 2010), gene cloning (Thind *et al.*, 2017), identification of horizontal gene transfer (Talianova *et al.*, 2012), PCR-based mapping of markers on individual chromosomal arms, genome sequencing (Martis *et al.*, 2013), and validation of whole-genome shotgun sequence assemblies (Kreplak *et al.*, 2019).

While the popularity of sex chromosome (laser) microdissection seems to dwindle nowadays, it is still a powerful tool to address many questions. The efficacy of laser microdissection extends seamlessly to other fields such as transcriptomics and proteomics, where precise tissue separation based on cellular anatomy or morphology is indispensable (reviewed in Misra *et al.*, 2014; Yin *et al.*, 2023). Overall, this method continues to be utilized in genomic analysis and is likely to remain a cost-effective choice for various genomic analysis, especially in non-model organisms with large genomes.

Cytogenetic tools to study sex-specific traits

Recent developments in cytogenetic techniques and significant advances in spatial resolution allowed researchers to study various aspects of plant genome architecture. Since Winge's identification of basic chromosome number in hop (*Humulus lupulus*; Winge, 1923) and Blackburn's detailed description of sex chromosome in *S. latifolia* (Blackburn, 1923)

cytogenetic applications were fundamental methods for rapid chromosome identification and sex chromosome characterization (Hobza *et al.*, 2018; Charlesworth and Charlesworth, 2020; Muyle *et al.*, 2022). With the combination of high-quality chromosome preparations from single root tip of a small seedlings or hairy root cell lines (for more details see Hobza and Vyskot, 2007; Bačovský *et al.*, 2018) and single leaves of living plants (Janousek *et al.*, 2022), it is possible to analyze karyotype of single plants. In this chapter, we describe the most used techniques of fluorescent *in situ* hybridisation (FISH) and discuss the need for correlation between DNA sequence and molecular data with the structure and organization of plant nuclei (Hobza *et al.*, 2015; Vyskot and Hobza, 2015). FISH is particularly suited to the study of single markers, low copy BACs, and repetitive sequences, i.e. (i) transposable elements (TEs) with dispersed genomic distribution, and (ii) tandem repeats (satellites) usually occupying isolated genomic loci (Figure 3).

The use of TEs for monitoring sex chromosome history

The key feature allowing the use of TEs in cytogenetic studies is their uneven distribution on sex chromosomes compared to autosomes (Cermak *et al.*, 2008; Filatov *et al.*, 2009; Steflova *et al.*, 2013; Kralova *et al.*, 2014; Kubat *et al.*, 2014), contrasting with the uniformity in genomes of hermaphroditic species (Cegan *et al.*, 2012, Wicker *et al.*, 2018; Flasch *et al.*, 2019). The likely cause is that TEs are preferentially active in either the male or female lineage as discussed elsewhere (Hobza *et al.*, 2017). The male-active TEs are therefore accumulating on the Y while simultaneously being underrepresented on the X chromosome, and *vice versa* for the female-active TEs. This allows TEs to be used (i) to estimate the size of the pseudoautosomal region (PAR), (ii) to determine the boundaries, and (iii) ages of evolutionary strata arising from the spread of the non-recombining region (Hobza *et al.*, 2015; Vyskot and Hobza, 2015). Early studies based on this principle were limited to a single TE (Filatov *et al.*, 2009) but by including diverse TE lineages a more detailed view can be obtained (Cermak *et al.*, 2008; Puterova *et al.*, 2018). This is because TE lineages active at different stages of sex chromosome evolution leave fingerprints (relative insertion densities) from which the history of non-recombining region expansion can be inferred. The conventional approach to investigate this phenomenon is multicolor FISH simultaneously analyzing multiple TE-derived probes. With the increasing availability of new cytological techniques and whole-genome assemblies, the precision of this approach can be expected to increase through a combination of super-resolution microscopy, such as structured illumination microscopy (SIM) and *in silico* analysis. *In silico* analysis requires precise annotation of individual TE lineages and must include assessment of their past transposition activity based on the determination of TE insertion ages (see below). When these conditions are met, TEs, alongside sex-linked genes, can become a powerful tool to study evolution of non-recombining sex chromosomes and to identify cryptic sex-linked regions in homomorphic sex chromosomes.

The satellite analysis in the context of sex chromosome biology

Repetitive sequences in non-recombining regions of sex chromosomes undergo rapid evolution, diversification, and expansion (Lengerova and Vyskot, 2001; Mariotti *et al.*, 2008; Navajas-Pérez *et al.*, 2009), followed by chromatin changes (Kubat *et al.*, 2008; Steflova *et al.*, 2013; Sacchi *et al.*, 2023, Preprint) and the formation of inactive chromatin regions visible as DAPI banding on the metaphase Y chromosomes (Jesionek *et al.*, 2021). The rapid expansion of repetitive sequences leads to genetic divergence and has far-reaching biological consequences, including the formation of reproductive barriers that further fix genetic differences (Kirkpatrick, 2017; O'Neill and O'Neill, 2018; Hooper *et al.*, 2019). It also allows the use of repeats to reconstruct the evolution of sex chromosomes at the interspecific level and within a species. The established starting point is the identification and characterization of repeats from short genomic reads by specialized bioinformatics tools (e.g. RepeatExplorer, see below) followed by physical mapping using multicolor FISH.

The most suitable candidates for these analyses are satellites creating large arrays in lengths of 10s to 1000s kb. Among satellites we also count robust cytogenetic marker of rDNA clusters (45S, 5S). The cytological mapping of 5S rDNA in *Rumex hastatulus* XY and XYY cytotype helped to identify autosomal pair that fused to sex chromosomes resulting in the formation of neo-XYY sex chromosome system (Grabowska-Joachimiak *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, phased assemblies of both *R. hastatulus* cytotypes revealed that neo-sex chromosomes in younger cytotypes (XYY) were formed by two events. An X-autosome fusion and a reciprocal translocation between homologous autosomes and the Y chromosome. These rearrangements were supported by physical localization of eight satellites indicating that the formation of the new cytotype was accompanied by chromosome shattering (Sacchi *et al.*, 2023, Preprint). Hence, both classes of DNA repeats (TEs and satellite clusters) provide fast information about genome reorganization and are valuable in the identification of chromosomal rearrangements during sex chromosome evolution (Fig. 3a).

Advances of chromosome-specific labeling

The most significant improvement in FISH application is the development of synthetic oligonucleotide probes (Fig. 3b, d) that are specific for chromosomal region(s), chromosomal arm(s), or whole chromosomes (Jiang and Gill, 2006; Jiang, 2019). With the increasing number of high-quality genome assemblies, such oligo painting probes are expected to become an important and essential tool to study genome evolution between related species as shown for *S. latifolia* and identification of XY-orthologous regions in *S. vulgaris* (Bačovský *et al.*, 2020). Recently, the oligo-painting probes helped to anchor Y-specific contigs in the genomic context of *S. latifolia* (Akagi *et al.*, 2023, Preprint).

Epigenomic landscape of sex chromatin

While most epigenetic methods used in the field of sex chromosome biology are adopted from model organisms, the application of these methods often brings surprising and pivotal conclusions regarding the divergence of XY chromosomes. In this regard, the question of whether epigenetic changes are the cause or consequence in the evolution of sex chromosomes and related phenomena, such as dosage compensation, is still unresolved (reviewed in Muyle *et al.*, 2017, 2022)

The term epigenetics represents all heritable and stable changes in gene expression that occur through alterations in chromatin structure and DNA methylation. These alterations are profoundly influenced by various developmental and environmental factors, driving spatio-temporal chromatin dynamics and overall structure of epigenomic landscape. We describe recent methodological improvements that increased our knowledge of sex chromosome epigenomics and discuss possible use of techniques that are being adopted now or in the near future in plant research.

Chromatin structure of plant sex chromosomes

Before the development of advanced NGS techniques, such as Chromatin Immunoprecipitation Sequencing (ChIP-seq), Methylated DNA immunoprecipitation sequencing (MeDIP-seq), and other next-generation sequencing based methods, the plant cytogeneticists were among the first researchers who studied sex chromosomes at the chromatin level. Indeed, early cytogenetic findings in *Silene* and *Rumex* revealed phenomena related to late replication of X chromosomes (Široký 1994, 1999) or formation of Y-chromosome bodies at the cell nucleus periphery in males (Lengerova and Vyskot, 2001; Vyskot and Hobza, 2015). A fresh perspective on immunolocalization involves the use of super-resolution microscopy techniques such as SIM and stimulated emission depletion microscopy (STED), which enable researchers to visualize objects beyond the diffraction limit of light. This innovative approach offers unprecedented clarity and detail, allowing for a deeper understanding of cellular structures and molecular interactions as was demonstrated for pericentromeric histone modifications and their Y chromosome localization in *Coccinia grandis* (Sousa *et al.*, 2016, 2017). Recent interest in the development of artificial intelligence (AI) assisted image analysis together with high-content imaging technology further opens new avenues in the research of various biological phenomena related e.g. in meiotic stability of sex chromosomes or tissue sectioning and plant development (Pegoraro and Misteli, 2017; Bitton *et al.*, 2021). Utilizing both, immunolabeling with high-content imaging remains to be adopted in plant sex chromosome research.

A complex screening of active and repressive histone marks can provide a missing link between early cytogenetic findings (Siroky *et al.*, 1999; Bačovský *et al.*, 2019) and RNA-seq studies (Muyle *et al.*, 2018). Such an approach can be later complemented by the already mentioned NGS technique(s) and its modification(s). By combining sequencing with Chromatin Immunoprecipitation assay (ChIP-seq) with appropriate antibodies against e.g. active histone modifications allows to decipher the evolutionary state of sex-linked genes and

their level of epidegeneration. ChIP is a robust method and can be considered an enrichment-based technique like DNA immunoprecipitation (DIP). Following ChIP protocol, DNA-bound protein is immunoprecipitated using a specific antibody, and the bound DNA is then coprecipitated for further analysis. Additionally, subsequent DNA purification allows the study of either selected genes through qRT-PCR, or an analysis of precipitated DNA using whole genome sequencing (Rodríguez Lorenzo *et al.*, 2020). Low Input and Single-cell methods are required sometimes due to limited plant material, e.g. endosperm studies or single meristematic tissues. A new and versatile method named Cleavage Under Targets and Release Using Nuclease (CUT&RUN) utilizes a new strategy apart from ChIP-seq. CUT&RUN targets Mnase to binding sites of the protein of interest through specific interactions, allowing it to have higher signal-to-background noise ratio and analysis of only thousands of cells per sample. CUT&RUN approach was successfully utilized in Arabidopsis as an alternative and efficient strategy for plant epigenomic studies but remains to be adopted for dioecious plant research (Zheng and Gehring, 2019).

Recently, the entire Y chromosome assembly complemented by bisulfite whole genome sequencing in *S. latifolia* helped to uncover the DNA methylation levels within the non-recombining region (Akagi *et al.*, 2023, Preprint; Moraga *et al.*, 2023, Preprint). Sodium bisulfite protocol has been widely used as a DNA methylation analysis for decades. This chemical deaminates non-methylated cytosines to uracil and leaves methylated cytosines unchanged. Compared to MeDIP, it allows a more accurate mapping and identification of methylation at single base resolution, as well as the average methylation level in the CG, CHG and CHH context and the identification of differentially methylated regions (DMRs). The main weakness of bisulfite modification is the impossibility to discriminate between methyl cytosine and other enzymatic oxidation derivatives (oxi-mC). Oxi-mC are present in significant amounts in plants and specific DNA modification protocols are available for each modification (Plongthongkum *et al.*, 2014; Wang *et al.*, 2015; Kalinka *et al.*, 2023).

Cutting edge sequencing technology of Oxford Nanopore Technology, Illumina short reads and Hi-C led to the fine-tuned genome assembly in a female willow tree (*Salix dunnii*) (He *et al.*, 2021). Sequencing techniques of 3rd generation represented by Single molecule real time sequencing (SMRT) from Pacific BioSciences and nanopore sequencing from Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) provide longer reads than conventional methods, starting from average length 10 Kb up to ultra-long reads over 100 Kb. Regardless of the detection specificity, both methods can identify epigenetic changes in the nucleotides without previous enrichment or chemical modification (Chen *et al.*, 2023). Combined with the length of the reads, these methods are becoming a promising tool in the sex chromosome epigenetics, including besides others the oxi-mC detection. Nevertheless, the functional role of these derivatives in the context of sex chromosome evolution remains to be elucidated.

An increasing knowledge of epigenetic mechanisms related to sex determination in poplar (Bräutigam *et al.*, 2017), melon (Latrasse *et al.*, 2017) and Japanese persimmon (Akagi *et al.*, 2016) shows the importance of chromatin analysis in studies focused on regulation of female and male development. Though the regulatory hierarchy of histone marks and DNA

methylation is still elusive, with the substantial improvements in genomics and cytogenetics, it is now possible to assess complex regulatory networks and to study remarkable evolutionary convergence of sex chromosomes.

Bioinformatics of sex chromosomes – unique tools and approaches

Due to the sex chromosome complexity and unique biology, it is necessary to develop and modify traditional bioinformatic tools to account for biological phenomena associated with sex chromosomes, specifically considering the segregation of X and Y (Z and W) and the presence of large region with suppressed recombination. The sequencing of complex regions of the Y (W) chromosome is challenging for assembly and subsequent analyses. This is illustrated by the history of assembling the human Y chromosome (the complete sequence was published recently in 2023, Rhie *et al.*, 2023). Indeed, reports on dioecious plant genome assemblies with repeat annotation of sex chromosomes are rather sparse so far. It is becoming increasingly apparent that overcoming these difficulties is a priority task, because detailed annotation of repeats can contribute significantly to understanding the evolution of sex chromosomes, for example the expansion of the Y non-recombining region as discussed above. In addition, sex chromosomes appear to be an excellent model system to study the biology of repeat accumulation and evolution, such as the causes of sex-biased TE activity (Kubat *et al.*, 2014; Hobza *et al.*, 2017) and the evolution of satellites located in different genomic contexts in terms of selection and recombination frequency (Jesionek *et al.*, 2021).

Repeats detection in full-length sex chromosome assemblies

The list of approaches utilized for repetitive DNA determination in assemblies of dioecious plant genomes is summarized in Supplementary Table S1. As can be seen for *R. hastatulus* and *Silene* spp., the most recent approaches for repeat detection in full-length plant sex chromosomes are especially based on employing the Extensive *de novo* TE Annotator (EDTA; Ou *et al.*, 2019). This tool has a capacity to reveal most of the transposons and their (super)families (LTR retrotransposons; terminal inverted repeats – TIRs; miniature inverted transposable elements – MITEs; and Helitrons). Nevertheless, when applied for TEs *de novo* identification without availability of species-specific TE library, the RepeatModeler2 (wrapped within EDTA) is called for generation of corresponding LTR retrotransposon sequences library. The TEs are coarsely designed as Ty1/Copia, Ty3/Gypsy and Unknown, requiring manual. Beside the complex EDTA pipeline, the RepeatMasker (Smit *et al.*, 2015) is employed using TE species specific library either generated *de novo* with RepeatModeler2 (*Cannabis sativa*, *Hippophae rhamnoides*, *Salix viminalis*, *S. cheanomeloides*, *S. arbutifolia*; Supplementary Table S1); or using available repeat elements from databases (TIGR Plant Repeat Databases, Ouyang and Buell, 2004; and/or RepBase, Bao *et al.*, 2015; e.g. *Carica papaya*, Supplementary Table S1).

Regardless of presence sex chromosomes, annotation of the dominant component of repeats in plant genomes, the LTR retrotransposons, suffer with (i) poor lineage level annotation (superfamily level only) and their (ii) full-length reconstruction from fragments due to multiple mutual nesting (e.g. Jedlicka *et al.*, 2019). A rather general affiliation into

superfamilies and/or unknown category can be fine-tuned using tools for LTR retrotransposon protein domains annotation as well as Domain based annotation of transposable elements (DANTE; <https://github.com/kavonrtep/dante>) and/or LTR retrotransposon classification tool like Tesorter (Zhang *et al.*, 2022). Even though most studies are avoiding the nested TEs analysis due to its complexity, there are some tools utilized for the successful assembly. One of them is the TE-greedy-nester (Lexa *et al.*, 2020), which employs an iterative greedy algorithm for full-length TEs reconstruction. The most reliable results this tool provides in combination with Tesorter and REXdb (Neumann *et al.*, 2019) as presented in TEs annotation of *Syzygium* tree genomes (Ouadi *et al.*, 2023).

Identification of repeats using short reads only – RepeatExplorer employment

Due to the above-mentioned obstacles with sex chromosome assemblies, so far the most conducted approaches started with RepeatExplorer (Novák *et al.*, 2010, 2013) run on low coverage short reads sequences (e.g. Puterova *et al.*, 2017, 2018; Jesionek *et al.*, 2021; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). These studies took the RE convenience of producing consensus sequences for (usually) full satellite monomers, which were in turn used for sex chromosome specific probes design and subsequent visualization with FISH. Beside the satellites, the clusters of LTR retrotransposon fragments were manually curated and used for reconstruction of partial- or full-length Ty3/*Gypsy* and Ty1/*Copia* retrotransposons (e.g. Puterova *et al.*, 2017, 2018). In summary, the most reliable approach for repetitive DNA detection is combination of reference repeat detection and annotation from both the assembled genomic and/or short reads sequences using combination of RepeatExplorer, RepeatModeler2, DANTE and Tesorter with subsequent run of robust pipelines as well as EDTA or RepeatMasker taking the convenience of obtained annotated references.

Sex-linked genes identification

Identification of sex-linked genes, sex determining regions and sex chromosome specific sequences can be done by different approaches (Supplementary Table S2) which can be divided in three main groups based on the input data (comparison of the coverage in male and female genomic data, transcriptomic or genomic sequences from defined crosses and association and SNP-based methods applied to natural populations). All the presented tools and their corresponding links, including pros and cons, are listed in Supplementary Table S2.

(i) Genomic approaches

One of the first described approaches to systematically discover Y chromosome genes was chromosome quotient (CQ) (Hall *et al.*, 2013). In the CQ method, genomic DNA from males and females is sequenced independently and aligned to candidate reference sequences. The female to male ratio of the number of alignments to a reference sequence is used to determine whether the sequence is Y-linked. Another option can be k-mer based approach which were used by Akagi *et al.* (2014, 2018) for identification of sex determining region in *Diospyros kaki* (Akagi *et al.*, 2014) and in kiwifruit (Akagi *et al.*, 2018). Briefly, reads from samples of the same gender were pooled and searched for the presence of gender-specific 35-bp k-mers.

Reads including male specific k-mers were assembled to generate Y-linked genomic contigs. Rangavittal *et al.* (2019) introduce a k-mer based method called DiscoverY, which combines proportion sharing with female reads with depth of coverage from male reads to classify contigs as Y-chromosomal. DiscoverY is an effective method to isolate Y-specific contigs from a whole-genome assembly. However, regions homologous to the X chromosome remain difficult to detect. Another recently developed tool is FindZX (Sigeman *et al.*, 2022) an automated Snakemake-based computational pipeline for sex chromosome identification and visualization through differences in genome coverage and heterozygosity between males and females.

(ii) Transcriptomic/expression-based approaches in controlled crosses

Transcriptomic approaches represent relatively cheap and very efficient tools for the study of sex determining systems in non-model organisms. Several tools were utilized to identify sex-linked genes and that are adopted for species without reference genome assembly.

LINKYX (Michalovova *et al.*, 2015) pipeline is based on the utilization of data obtained by transcriptome sequencing of parents and separately pooled male and female progeny. The main aim of this pipeline is to identify putatively sex-linked markers that should be further experimentally tested. Apart of the X (or Z-linked) linked SNPs that are identified with LINKYX_X variant of the pipeline, LinkYX enables to identify putatively sex specific genes (Y-specific or W-specific) based on the quantitative study of transcription level in parents and in the dataset of pooled male and female progeny (LINKYX_Y). LINKYX_X and LinkYX have been successfully applied to the studies of sex determination in *S. otites*, *S. borysthena* and *S. colpophylla* (Balounova *et al.*, 2019). SEX-DETECTOR and SEX-DETECTOR++ (Muyle *et al.*, 2016) are, similarly to LINKYX, based on the study of the transcriptomes in the population obtained by controlled cross. This method has been shown to work well with as few as five offspring of each sex and has successfully been used in several dioecious species (Muyle *et al.*, 2018; Martin *et al.*, 2019; Veltsos, 2019; Badouin *et al.*, 2020; Fruchard *et al.*, 2020; Prentout *et al.*, 2020). SEX-DETECTOR and its updated version can in fact be used for multiple purposes: identification of sex-linked genes and sex chromosomes in studied organism (XY or ZW), haplotypes reconstruction of the gametolog copies, and estimation of allelic expression of each of the copies. However, because of its requirement of controlled cross, the use of this method is limited to species that can be easily bred or cultivated in controlled conditions. Therefore, this approach hinders its application to species with long generation time.

(iii) Association and SNP based methods in wild populations

To characterize the sex-determination system the genome wide association studies (GWAS) were used in several species (e.g. *Salix nigra*; Sanderson *et al.*, 2021); *Dioscorea alata* (Mondo *et al.*, 2021); *P. euphratica* and *P. alba* (Yang *et al.*, 2020). As an input the genomic sequences, DarTSeq reads (Diversity array technology) and capture array were used for mapping to reference sequences. For usage of restriction site-associated DNA sequencing data to study sex determination a computational workflow RADSex (Feron *et al.*, 2021) was

developed. This tool was developed for Japanese medaka (*Oryza latipes*) (Feron *et al.*, 2021) but it can be adopted in other species, including plants. Sex specific markers can be further identified with the Double digest restriction-site associated DNA sequencing (DdRADseq), method that was used in *Nepenthes* (Scharmann *et al.*, 2019) and *Amaranthus* (Montgomery *et al.*, 2019). To improve the robustness and transparency in sex-linked sequences identification, Grayson *et al.* (2022, Preprint) prepared a comprehensive workflow called SexFindR. This workflow combines coverage-based analysis and a variety of population genomic analyses such as the reference-based SNP density, GWAS, and FST, as well as the reference-free kmers GWAS to screen for common candidate sex-linked regions. Sdpop (Käfer *et al.*, 2021) has similar goals as SEX-DETECTOR and SEX-DETECTOR++ but is based on different models and so it enables identification of sex-linked transcripts in natural populations. This approach has been used to study sex chromosomes in *Amborella trichopoda* (Käfer *et al.*, 2022).

New bioinformatics tools and approaches substantially increased the number of dioecious plants identified to date. These tools helped to characterize biological nature of sex chromosomes, leading to important discoveries in epigenetics and functional genomics, enabling the study of sex-linked genes through genome editing. In the last chapter, we summarize the historical and the most used techniques in the field of functional genetics and discuss its future direction.

Functional genetics of plant sex chromosomes

Sex chromosomes carry the decisive information whether the individual will become male or female, however, the functional studies of plant sex chromosomes and sex-linked genes are generally not straightforward tasks. While classical genetics rely on recombination mapping for identifying causal genes, this approach is largely unfeasible as sex-linked genes are located within non-recombining region. Moreover, extensive accumulation of transposable elements and/or tandem repeats makes genome assembly difficult, which is especially the case of Y/W chromosomes (for details see previous chapters). On the other hand, the scientific community developed and applied diverse strategies to overcome the issues related to studying functional aspects of plant sex chromosomes (Fig. 4a–e).

Classical strategies to study functional aspects of plant sex chromosomes

Although cytogenetic techniques allowed the identification of heteromorphic sex chromosomes in numerous plant species (for review see Ming *et al.*, 2011), their role in the sex determination mechanism was not immediately clear. Initially, phenotypic analyses of individuals with numerical chromosomal abnormalities were essential for deciphering the contribution of particular chromosomes to sex determination (Parker and Clark, 1991). The polyploid and aneuploid plants are key materials to elucidate whether the sex is determined by active Y/W chromosome (as in humans) or by X:autosome ratio (the system known from *Drosophila*). The active Y (W) chromosome has been observed in the majority of dioecious plants, eg., *Carica papaya* (Hofmeyr and van Elden, 1942; Hofmeyr, 1944), *Coccinia grandis* (Kumar and Viseveshwaraiah, 1952) *Silene latifolia* (Ono, 1939; Warmke and Blakeslee,

1939; Westergaard, 1940), *Silene otites* (Warmke, 1942), *Populus tremula* (Johnsson, 1940, 1942, 1945) etc. Conversely, the X:autosome type that is characterized by no effect of Y(W) on sex determination, seems to be infrequent in plants, as it was confirmed only in hop (genus *Humulus*; Neve, 1961; Shephard *et al.*, 2000) and several sorrel species (such as *Rumex acetosa* or *Rumex hastatulus*; (Ono, 1928; Smith, 1963). Despite the studies of polyploids and/or aneuploids mostly explored the sex determination systems solely on the broad level of whole chromosomes, this classical methodical approach undoubtedly laid the cornerstone of plant sex chromosome research (Fig. 4a).

Deletion mutants represent another significant methodical step toward understanding the function of plant sex chromosomes (Fig. 4b). In the seminal experiments, Mogens Westergaard obtained *S. latifolia* individuals harboring Y-chromosome deletions (Westergaard, 1946a; 1946b, 1948), some of which resulted in remarkable sexual phenotypes. Plants with missing distal part of the Y p-arm developed hermaphroditic flowers, whereas the absence of the proximal segment of the same arm led to the formation of asexual flowers. Based on these observations, Westergaard defined gynoeceium suppression factor (GSF) and stamen promoting factor (SPF). Westergaard's results provided the first mechanistic evidence that two separate loci are involved in the establishment of dioecy. As such, the so-called "two-gene model" for the evolution of dioecy was proposed based on these findings (Westergaard, 1953; Charlesworth and Charlesworth, 1978) and *S. latifolia* became a textbook example for explaining sex determination in plants.

The analyses of Y-linked deletions became a fundamental approach to studying the sex determination in *S. latifolia* (Donnison *et al.*, 1996; Lardon *et al.*, 1999; Lebel-Hardenack *et al.*, 2002; Zluvova *et al.*, 2007; Fujita *et al.*, 2012; Kazama *et al.*, 2016). The mutations were induced by X-irradiation, γ -irradiation, or heavy ion beam irradiation, all of which create deletions spanning relatively short genomic regions, allowing more precise mapping and marker identification (Fig. 4b). In addition, a thorough characterization of these deletion mutants was carried out including extensive cytogenetic and histological analyses, spatiotemporal gene expression profiling, and electron microscopy (Zluvova *et al.*, 2006; Koizumi *et al.*, 2010). By combining comprehensive phenotyping with physical mapping techniques, the detailed map of *S. latifolia* Y chromosome was constructed (Kazama *et al.*, 2016) and recently, the comparative genomics using wild-type plants and deletion mutants led to the identification of candidate genes for sex determination (Kazama *et al.*, 2022; Akagi *et al.*, 2023, Preprint; Moraga *et al.*, 2023, Preprint). Deletion mutants are a powerful tool for the identification of sex determining genes especially in the species with small non-recombining regions as described in *Asparagus* (Harkess *et al.*, 2017, 2020).

Interestingly, in some cases it is possible to obtain Y-chromosome linked deletions caused by storage of pollen in inappropriate conditions. This phenomenon has been described in *S. latifolia* as one of the causes of hermaphroditism (gerontogony) (van Nigtevecht, 1966). It is possible to hypothesize that the non-recombining regions can be prone to various kinds of genetic damage. This phenomenon has not yet been studied on a detailed level. There is even no proper data from irradiation experiments as the analyses were always focused on the

plants showing aberrant phenotypes in the first generation which leads to a high prevalence of Y-deletions in the further studied material and the frequency of autosomal deletions with recessive phenotype remained unknown.

Some level of phenotypic instability is present in most plant sex determining systems (Delph and Meagher, 1995). Spontaneously originated hermaphrodites enabled to ascertain the type of heterogamety in some species (e.g. in *S. dioica*), already at the beginnings of genetics (Shull, 1911). In *S. latifolia*, androhermaphrodites were successfully induced by global genome demethylation and/or inhibiting histone deacetylation (Janousek *et al.*, 1996; Bačovský *et al.*, 2022). Likewise, the (imperfect) stamen development can be activated in female plants using silver thiosulfate (Law *et al.*, 2002) and *Microbotryum* infection (Strassburger, 1900; Uchida *et al.*, 2003). Putative female suppressor gene was identified in dioecious buffalo grass (*Bouteloua dactyloides*) using pistil smut (*Salmacisia buchloëana*) induced androhermaphrodites (Chandra and Huff, 2010). Both andro- and gynohermaphrodites represent remarkable tools for studying sex determination and sex-specific development, because, apart from deletion mutants, they contain complete genomes (Fig. 4d, e). For example, a process of stamen development can be studied in XX background as well as gynoeceium formation in individuals harboring Y chromosome (Law *et al.*, 2002; Uchida *et al.*, 2003; Kazama *et al.*, 2005; Zemp *et al.*, 2015; Bačovský *et al.*, 2022) (Fig. 4).

So far not yet a widely exploited strategy for the study of the evolution of sex determining systems from a functional point of view is study of interspecific hybrids. The sex-linked genes are often subject to adaptive evolution (Zemp *et al.*, 2018; Muyle *et al.*, 2021) and their change can probably influence the rest of the genome (Žlůvová *et al.*, 2021). These changes can be visualized in inter-specific hybrids between dioecious species and their hermaphrodite relatives, e.g. the similar histological phenotypes were observed in some deletion mutants in *S. latifolia* and in the interspecific hybrid between *S. latifolia* female and *S. viscosa* male (Zlůvová *et al.*, 2005). The divergent evolution of the genes related with sexual dimorphism can be observed even in closely related species (Demuth *et al.*, 2014; Baena-Díaz *et al.*, 2019; Liu *et al.*, 2020). The divergent gene evolution in very closely related dioecious species can be revealed on a phenotypic level in subsequent generations of brother sister mating after interspecific crosses (Winge, 1931). This process overcomes functional redundancy widely present in plant genomes and reveals complex interactions between genes in pathways involved in sex determination and sexual dimorphism. So far not undertaken combined phenotypical, genetic and genomic analysis of recombinant inbred lines (for a review see Pollard, 2012) of related dioecious species could shed new light on the complex evolution of sex chromosomes and the rest of the genomes of dioecious species both from qualitative and quantitative point of view.

Reverse genetic tools for investigating the function of sex-linked genes

Identification of sex-linked genes with aforementioned bioinformatic and NGS methods has opened the door to reverse genetic studies (Fig. 4c). However, none of the dioecious plants with the sex chromosomes have become a broadly used model system in molecular biology. Therefore, the easily accessible methodical tools for solving complex questions related to sex

chromosome function are still missing. Candidate genes for sex determination have been described in still increasing number of dioecious plants including *Diospyrus* (Akagi *et al.*, 2014, 2016), *Asparagus* (Harkess *et al.*, 2017, 2020), date palm (Torres *et al.*, 2018), poplar (Müller *et al.*, 2020; Xue *et al.*, 2020), willow (Sanderson *et al.*, 2021; Hu *et al.*, 2023), kiwifruit (Akagi *et al.*, 2018, 2019), *Silene* (Kazama *et al.*, 2022; Akagi *et al.*, 2023, Preprint; Moraga *et al.*, 2023, Preprint) and many others. Although CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing represents a very powerful tool in model organisms, the functional evaluation of putative plant sex determination genes has been accomplished so far only in poplar (Müller *et al.*, 2020). Most candidate genes were evaluated by heterologous expression either in *Arabidopsis* or tobacco (Akagi *et al.*, 2014, 2018, 2019; Kazama *et al.*, 2022). In *S. latifolia*, a combination of virus-induced gene silencing (Akagi *et al.*, 2023, Preprint) and shoot apical meristem treatment with synthetic peptides. Kazama *et al.* (2022) suggested the role of *CLAVATA3* gene in gynoecium suppression. Interestingly, these studies showed that the divergence of sex chromosomes led to the loss of function in X-linked copy whereas Y-copy of *CLAVATA3* remained conserved and fully functional. Though the treatment with synthetic peptides did not lead to complete organ suppression in females, it is a suitable tool for models in which genome engineering is not possible, inefficient, or time-consuming, such as *S. latifolia* (Hudzieczek *et al.*, 2019). With the increasing number of new tools in functional genetics, more biological phenomena associated with plant sex chromosomes such as sexual antagonism, dosage compensation or sexual dimorphism will be investigated from the functional perspective. Such areas can be examined from a new angle, offering valuable insights into their complex mechanisms and evolution.

Conclusion

This review highlights methodical approaches that are adjusted, utilized or entirely developed *de novo* for the purpose of sex chromosome analyses in plants. Investigation of plant sex chromosomes often requires adapting the current methods and optimizing their use for dioecious species as in the case of CRISPR/Cas9 technology discussed above (Fig. 4c). As more sophisticated genetic engineering tools are still emerging (Capdeville *et al.*, 2023) and are being adopted to non-model species (Lee and Wang, 2023; Yan *et al.*, 2023), we will likely witness extensive functional genetic studies of plant sex chromosomes in the near future. Newly developed NGS techniques and bioinformatic workflows are invaluable for genome comparative analysis, transcription profiling, and epigenomic studies regarding sex chromosome evolution. It can be anticipated that the integration of diverse methods from various disciplines, as recently elucidated in the genus *Cucumis* (Pichot *et al.*, 2022), will provide a more comprehensive understanding of chromatin regulation and sex chromosome compartmentalization within the genome of studied organisms, thereby allowing for a careful rediscovery and revision of important biological questions regarding sex chromosome origin.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Author contribution

R.H. created and structured the main concept and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. All authors contributed equally to manuscript writing and revision, read and approved the submitted version.

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Figure 1. Schematic diagram of sex chromosome evolution in dioecious plants. Species are shown according to their level of sex chromosome differentiation and Y chromosome asynapsis. In *S. oleracea*, *A. officinalis* and *C. papaya*, the sex chromosomes are mostly homomorphic with recently formed non-recombining regions (region with suppressed recombination). The non-recombining region is largely extended almost to entire chromosomal length in species with heteromorphic sex chromosomes, namely in *S. latifolia*, *R. hastatulus* (XY cytotype), *R. acetosa*, *H. lupulus*, *H. japonicus* and *M. polymorpha*. The position of the centromere, the PAR length and the ratio between X and Y is illustrative.

Figure 2. Laser microdissection as a tool to reduce genome complexity. Sex chromosomes in metaphase are isolated from plant cells (mostly pollen mother cells or root tips) and subsequently spread on a special microscopic slide covered with the membrane. After microdissection, chromosomes are transferred into a tube and processed to other applications. In case of chromosome sorting, the chromosome suspension is stained with a DNA-specific dye and introduced into a flow chamber. Within this chamber, individual chromosomes interact with a laser beam, and the scattered light and emitted fluorescence are measured. Through this process, a histogram of fluorescence intensity (known as a flow karyotype) is generated. Sorting is accomplished by breaking the liquid stream into droplets and electrically charging the droplets containing the chromosomes of interest.

Figure 3. Cytogenetic tools to study sex chromosome origin and evolution. Cytogenetics nowadays combine genomic tools to study repeat fraction including TEs and satellites (a), design unique barcodes to distinguish particular chromosome or chromosomal domain using chromosome oligo-painting probe design (b), and bioinformatic tools to dissect single chromosomes or genome parts (c). The combination of above methods helps to understand sex chromosome evolution regarding their autosomal origin, chromosomal rearrangements, and Y(W) chromosome differentiation. Arrows represent evolutionary steps during sex chromosome divergence (d). The sex chromosome barcoding allows understanding of meiotic pairing which in turn supports chromosomal fusions and inversion/translocations. To chromosomes belong to species with references, from the top to the bottom as follows: *S. latifolia* Ogre retroelement (Kubat *et al.*, 2014), *R. hastatulus* XY cytotype satellite C1135 (Sacchi *et al.*, 2023, Preprint), *S. latifolia* PAR oligo-painting probe with the subtelomeric satellite X43.1 and centromeric satellite STAR-C (Bačovský *et al.*, 2020), and the same DNA probes on chromosomes in metaphase I in *S. latifolia* (Bernasconi *et al.*, 2009; Bačovský *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 4. Methodical strategies to assess the function of sex chromosomes in plants. Experimental assays with polyploids (alternatively aneuploids) represent the classical way to determine the role of individual sex chromosomes (a). These assays with plants of various ploidy levels were usually supported by analyses of deletion lines (plants carrying short-chromosomal deletions or microdeletions) (b) that allowed researchers to identify sex-linked regions involved in sex determination and floral development. Modern assays using reverse genetics, such as CRISPR/Cas9, virus-induced gene silencing (VIGS) or peptide treatment of shoot apical meristem (c) provide direct evidence of the gene function and its contribution to the development of reproductive organs. Parasite infected (d) or chemically induced (e) hermaphrodites from either female or male individuals, e.g. in *Silene* or kaki, let to the identification of key mechanisms and genes that regulate sexual phenotypes, and to understand the regulatory networks leading to separate sexes.

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Figure 1

Species	Chromosome differentiation	
<p><i>Asparagus officinalis</i> (Ma et al. 2022)</p>		
<p><i>Carica papaya</i> (Zhang et al. 2008)</p>		
<p><i>Silene latifolia</i> (Lengerova et al. 2003)</p>		
<p><i>Rumex hastatulus</i> XY cytotype (Cunado et al. 2007)</p>		
<p><i>Rumex acetosa</i> (Kasjaniuk et al. 2019, Sacchi et al. 2023)</p>		
<p><i>Humulus lupulus</i> (Divashuk et al. 2011)</p>		
<p><i>Humulus japonicus</i> (Alexandrov et al. 2012)</p>		
<p><i>Marchantia polymorpha</i> (Katsuyuki et al. 2012)</p>		

 XY pairing
 Male specific region on the Y/heterochromatic knob in MSY
 Tandem repeat/satellite
 X/Y specific contig

Figure 2. Laser microdissection as a tool to reduce genome complexity. Sex chromosomes in metaphase are isolated from plant cells (mostly pollen mother cells or root tips) and subsequently spread on a special microscopic slide covered with the membrane. After microdissection, chromosomes are transferred into a tube and processed to other applications. In case of chromosome sorting, the chromosome suspension is stained with a DNA-specific dye and introduced into a flow chamber. Within this chamber, individual chromosomes interact with a laser beam, and the scattered light and emitted fluorescence are measured. Through this process, a histogram of fluorescence intensity (known as a flow karyotype) is generated. Sorting is accomplished by breaking the liquid stream into droplets and electrically charging the droplets containing the chromosomes of interest.

Figure 3

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Figure 4

